

Extraction of Anthocyanins from Aparajita flowers and their complexation with Metal

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Abstract:

Anthocyanins, color pigments present in plants, are highly utilized flavonoid group of compounds known for their physical, chemical and biological properties. Various nutraceutical, pharmaceutical, and cosmeceutical industries utilize anthocyanins as natural colorants and/or for their biological functions. Anthocyanins in the flower are made up of basic classes as pelargonidin is responsible for orange-red colour, cyanidin for red hues and delphinidin for lilac to blue hues. In this study, the objective of an efficient, low-cost, and eco-friendly method of anthocyanin pigment extraction from Aparajita flowers and stabilising it with chelation with inorganic salts of metals with the perspective of food application has been embraced. In Aparajita flowers, rare blue anthocyanin exist, which if extracted and stabilised in its intrinsic color, can provide very demanding blue color for food and beverages industry.

Keywords: Color, Anthocyanin, Inorganic salts, Chelation, stable natural color, food industry

1. Introduction

Anthocyanins are glycosylated forms of anthocyanidins, normally occurring as 3-glycosides or 3,5-diglycosides. Anthocyanins are the most frequently studied flavylum dyes because they are the largest class of water-soluble compounds present in the plant kingdom and are responsible for a range of colors in plants, from orange-red to purple-blue (Harborne and Williams 2000).

In addition, anthocyanins protect plants from several biotic and abiotic stresses (Ahmed, Park et al. 2014), (Chalker-Scott 1999). Anthocyanins may act as photo protective agents by absorbing excess visible and UV light, preventing the formation of free radicals that may affect plant tissues by compromising photosynthesis (Guo and Wang 2010), (Zhu, Zhang et al. 2018). Because of their recognized antioxidant properties, anthocyanins may also be

important in maintaining the integrity of membranes in fruits and vegetables during the postharvest period, decelerating cell senescence (Tilbrook and Tyerman 2008). In addition, the consumption of anthocyanin-rich foods has been associated with numerous beneficial health effects owing to the multiple biological properties of these compounds (e.g., anti-proliferative, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties) (Fernandes, Pérez-Gregorio et al. 2017), (Bars-Cortina, Sakhawat et al. 2022), (Oliveira, Fernandes et al. 2015). Colors of the anthocyanins depend on the pH of the solution because the structure of the anthocyanins alters depending on the pH of the surrounding medium (Khoo, Azlan et al. 2017).

Anthocyanins have been used in traditional medicine and for colouring food since ancient times. The therapeutic effects of anthocyanins are mainly attributed to their antioxidant activities (Khoo, Azlan et al. 2017). Anthocyanins are the most abundant flavonoid type in human diets and benefit human wellness from multiple aspects. Nevertheless, the application of anthocyanins is currently limited by its low bioavailability and stability outside of flowers and in human bodies (Li, Wang et al. 2021). Blue color in nature is rare commodity as it's very unstable outside its natural tenancy. Blue color/Anthocyanin found in some flowers can be worked upon to study its recovery and further use on food and beverages industry.

Clitoria ternatea plant is commonly grown as an ornamental plant and possesses great medicinal value. Its flower is edible and also known as blue pea or butterfly pea flower. *Clitoria ternatea* L. commonly known as butterfly pea or blue pea is a perennial leguminous herb belonging to family Fabaceae having several beneficial agricultural and medical applications, such as fodder, nitrogen-fixing crop, an eco-friendly insecticide (Oguis, Gilding et al. 2019), food colouring (Pham, Nguyen et al. 2019) and in traditional medicine for disorders such as anasarca and ascites (Lakshan, Jayanath et al. 2019). It is commonly grown as an ornamental plant. Polyacylated derivatives of delphinidin 3,3',5'-triglucoside, named "ternatins" are the major anthocyanins present in blue pea flower (Terahara, Saito et al. 1990) (Vidana Gamage, Lim et al. 2022). The unique feature of anthocyanins present in blue pea flowers is the high abundance of polyacylated anthocyanins known as ternatins. Ternatins give the flowers their vibrant blue color and were discovered in 1985 (Saito, Abe et al. 1985).

Aparajita (*Clitoria ternatea*) flowers are used as anthocyanin source in this study and they have been tried to complex with copper and alum to increase their stability and their stability/quality has been checked by spectroscopic methods. This work also investigated a

strategy to develop efficient and sustainable processes for extracting anthocyanins from blue *Clitoria* flowers while maintaining thermal stability of its color.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Plant material

Blue coloured, fully bloomed, disease free, and undamaged healthy flowers of *Clitoria ternatea* L. (Aparajita blue flower) were procured from the local flower market, Kanpur, India and they were kept in cold (20°C) and dark storage until processed (the shelf life was found to be for a week).

2.1.2 Chemicals and Glassware

All the chemicals (Methanol, Copper sulphate, Alum etc.) were procured from S D Fine chemicals in Kanpur and all are of analytical grade. All the glassware used is of Borosil make.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Moisture Content Analysis

Aparajita flowers are taken to determine the moisture content. 100 gm of the flowers were kept in an oven at 100°C for 5 to 6 hrs and then weighed. The procedure was repeated three times to get a constant weight. Percentage moisture was calculate with the help of following equation –

$$\text{Moisture content} = (\text{wet wt.} - \text{dry wt.} / \text{wet wt.}) * 100$$

2.2.2 Anthocyanin extraction

Anthocyanin extraction was carried out by acidic methanol. The green part of the flowers i.e. green corolla of Aparajita was removed before extraction as only petals will be needed in anthocyanin extraction. Then the flower petals were immersed in acidic methanol (0.1% HCl (v/v) in methanol) for 2 to 3 hrs at room temperature, in darkness without heating or stirring. The mixture was filtered on a Buchner funnel and the remaining solids were washed with 0.1% HCl in methanol until a clear solution was obtained (Longo, Scardino et al. 2007). For full recovery of Colorant/anthocyanin flower material was little heated (35°C) in the end. The combined filtrates were little concentrated and used for metal complexation and spectroscopic analysis.

2.2.3 Quantification of Anthocyanin

Anthocyanin so extracted was dried in preweighed beaker at 50°C in an oven and weighed after drying. The procedure was repeated three times to get a constant weight. This value can be proposed as rough quantity of anthocyanin of the flowers.

2.2.4 Metal Complexation of Anthocyanin

For chelating metal entities to Anthocyanin, inorganic salts solutions were prepared in deionized water. 100ppm solutions of Alum and copper sulphate were prepared by dissolving accurate quantity (100mg of salt in 100 ml of DI water) of salt in DI water and then diluting it further to get desired concentration. After salt solution preparation, it was stabilised (kept for a while) and then mixed with anthocyanin solution and kept in dark for 1 hrs after thorough mixing.

2.2.5 Spectroscopic analysis of color extracts

UV-Visible analysis of intrinsic methanolic extract of anthocyanin of Aparajita flowers was carried out. The presence of colorant and metal complexes was also checked by spectroscopic analysis of the each extract. Anthocyanin extract were diluted with little acidified methanol and then UV VIS analysis was carried out while acidified methanol was taken as blank. The UV VIS analysis was carried out on UV VIS 1800 Shimadzu model spectrophotometer at a resolution of 1 nm.

IR analysis was also carried out for anthocyanin (Aparajita) as well as metal complexes of anthocyanin on Spectrum Two (ATR) Model of Perkin Elmer.

3. Results and Discussion:

Anthocyanin extraction and their stability are of great concern. Thus their extraction with mild agent and their stabilising through metal chelation has been tried. A very low concentration of Copper sulphate and Alum are used to complex extracted anthocyanin from Aparajita Flowers.

Anthocyanin from Aparajita/Clitoria Flower

Anthocyanin was extracted with 1% acidic methanol. The purpose of acidification is to denature the membranes of the cell wall where the anthocyanin is maximally located. The blue flowers peculiarly yielded dark red anthocyanin extract in acidic conditions. As observed, like all anthocyanins, the colour of Aparajita flower anthocyanin extract also changes with pH. At lower pH the dark red color exists, at mild acidic pH (around 4.5-5.5) the purplish color start to appear and at alkaline pH (6.5-8) a strong blue color takes hold

which on further increasing pH changes to light greenish. This colour change could be explained by the structural alteration occurring in anthocyanin molecules along with the change in H^+ and OH^- concentration in the medium. The red colour is attributed to the presence of flavylium ion, blue colour to the presence of the neutral quinoidal base and the green colour to ionic chalcone (Bridle and Timberlake 1997). In non-acylated anthocyanins, flavylium ion transforms to colourless carbinol pseudo base when pH increases. But in blue Aparajita flower anthocyanins, the presence of acyl groups prevents the hydrolysis of flavylium ion to less stable carbinol pseudo base form and instead form the blue colour quinoidal that possess less sensitivity to pH changes in mildly acidic or neutral medium (figure 1).

Figure 1: Structural change of delphinidin-3-glucoside with increasing pH in *Clitoria* Path (A,B) shows the transformation of flavylium ion to carbinol or pseudo base. Path (A,C) shows the transformation of flavylium ion to quinoidal base (Vidana Gamage, Lim et al. 2021)

Metal Chelation and Spectroscopic Analysis

The effect of Metal chelation on extracted anthocyanin of Aparajita flowers was observed with spectroscopic analysis. Their spectra are observed with very sharp peaks of Anthocyanin in intrinsic extract and changes in UV region after metal addition. These peaks

range from 520nm to 550nm before and after metal addition (Fig.2-4). The addition of Copper Sulphate and alum increased conjugation as can be observed with increase absorbance and multiple peaks in UV region. The more the conjugation more stable will be the molecule. Visible region peak remain at almost same wavelength in all metal complexed anthocyanin samples. These metal entities obviously may/will increase shelf life of Anthocyanin.

Figure 2. UV Vis of Aparajita Anthocyanin

Figure 3. UV Vis of Aparajita Anthocyanin+CuSO₄

Figure 4. UV Vis of Aparajita Anthocyanin+Alum

Every IR spectra has shown intense peaks at 3500 (hydroxyl group) and at 1710 cm (carbonyl group) and that of metal chelated anthocyanin has less intense peaks at these wavelengths which may be due to complexation of O-hydroxy carbonyl moiety of the anthocyanin molecules (Figure 5, 6, 7).

Figure 5. IR of Aparajita Anthocyanin

Figure 6. IR of Aparajita Anthocyanin+CuSO₄

Figure 7. IR of Aparajita Anthocyanin+Alum

Typically, anthocyanins are unstable in solution, especially under conditions where blue colouration could potentially be observed. This is due to the rapid formation of colourless forms, and the eventual isomerisation into yellow forms, leading to browning of products. To stabilise the anthocyanin quinonoid base and generate blue colours, anthocyanins form complexes through intramolecular co-pigmentation, and metal chelation. Many of these

strategies have been adopted in nature by plants that produce blue flowers or fruit (Houghton, Appelhagen et al. 2021).

The complexes formed between metal ions and anthocyanins can be very complicated structures since a variety of intramolecular and intermolecular copigmentation interactions can occur. Generally, metal ions increased the color stability of anthocyanins, particularly at selected pH. Petunidin derivative metal chelates produced a wide range of colors with enhanced stability (Tang and Giusti 2020).

In nature, many plants have anthocyanin color-stabilizing mechanisms to maintain their red and blue colors. These mechanisms include intermolecular and intramolecular copigmentation, self-association, and metal complexation (Yoshida, Mori et al. 2009), which are usually driven by several noncovalent interactions, such as hydrogen bonding, van der Waals, π - π stacking, and metal-ligand interactions and hydrophobic effect (Cruz, Basílio et al. 2021). Copigmentation is also a widely accepted concept of anthocyanin stabilization. In particular, π - π interactions with electron-rich colorless phenolics are an exceptional phenomenon of anthocyanins, shifting wavelength of maximum absorption to more bluish hues (bathochromic effect) and increasing intensity (hyperchromic effect) at slightly acidic pH values. High copigment concentrations and the unique conditions in vacuoles may lead to intense and stable blue flower and petal hues as in *Clitoria*.

4. Conclusions:

Aparajita flowers/ butterfly pea flowers are used traditionally as herbal tea in Southeast Asia, and thus have a history of safe consumption, with accompanying anecdotal health benefits. Its anthocyanin extracted by mild process and stabilised/chelated with Alum and copper. It has been observed that after metal chelation *Clitoria* anthocyanin become somewhat stable as decipher through UV VIS and IR study. Its chemical constitution changes slightly which increases its stability in turn indicated its potential to be used as natural food dye. This kind of study is beneficial for better and sustainable dyes/materials to replace food color processing with low chemical consuming ways to figure out ecofriendly and consumer friendly edible dye processing techniques.

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7. References:

- Ahmed, N. U., J.-I. Park, H.-J. Jung, T.-J. Yang, Y. Hur and I.-S. Nou (2014). "Characterization of dihydroflavonol 4-reductase (DFR) genes and their association with cold and freezing stress in *Brassica rapa*." *Gene* 550(1): 46-55.
- Bars-Cortina, D., A. Sakhawat, C. Pinol-Felis and M.-J. Motilva (2022). Chemopreventive effects of anthocyanins on colorectal and breast cancer: A review. *Seminars in Cancer Biology*, Elsevier.
- Bridle, P. and C. Timberlake (1997). "Anthocyanins as natural food colours—selected aspects." *Food chemistry* 58(1-2): 103-109.
- Chalker-Scott, L. (1999). "Environmental significance of anthocyanins in plant stress responses." *Photochemistry and photobiology* 70(1): 1-9.
- Cruz, L., N. Basílio, N. Mateus, V. De Freitas and F. Pina (2021). "Natural and synthetic flavylium-based dyes: The chemistry behind the color." *Chemical Reviews* 122(1): 1416-1481.
- Fernandes, I., R. Pérez-Gregorio, S. Soares, N. Mateus and V. De Freitas (2017). "Wine flavonoids in health and disease prevention." *Molecules* 22(2): 292.
- Guo, J. and M.-H. Wang (2010). "Ultraviolet A-specific induction of anthocyanin biosynthesis and PAL expression in tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.)." *Plant growth regulation* 62: 1-8.
- Harborne, J. B. and C. A. Williams (2000). "Advances in flavonoid research since 1992." *Phytochemistry* 55(6): 481-504.
- Houghton, A., I. Appelhagen and C. Martin (2021). "Natural blues: Structure meets function in anthocyanins." *Plants* 10(4): 726.
- Khoo, H. E., A. Azlan, S. T. Tang and S. M. Lim (2017). "Anthocyanidins and anthocyanins: Colored pigments as food, pharmaceutical ingredients, and the potential health benefits." *Food & nutrition research* 61(1): 1361779.
- Lakshan, S. A. T., N. Y. Jayanath, W. P. K. M. Abeysekera and W. K. S. M. Abeysekera (2019). "A commercial potential blue pea (*Clitoria ternatea* L.) flower extract incorporated beverage having functional properties." *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine* 2019.

- Li, B., L. Wang, W. Bai, W. Chen, F. Chen, C. Shu, B. Li, L. Wang, W. Bai and W. Chen (2021). "Bioavailability and Bioabsorption of Anthocyanins." *Anthocyanins: Chemistry, Processing & Bioactivity*: 95-113.
- Longo, L., A. Scardino and G. Vasapollo (2007). "Identification and quantification of anthocyanins in the berries of *Pistacia lentiscus* L., *Phillyrea latifolia* L. and *Rubia peregrina* L." *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies* 8(3): 360-364.
- Oguis, G. K., E. K. Gilding, M. A. Jackson and D. J. Craik (2019). "Butterfly pea (*Clitoria ternatea*), a cyclotide-bearing plant with applications in agriculture and medicine." *Frontiers in plant science* 10: 448370.
- Oliveira, H., I. Fernandes, V. de Freitas and N. Mateus (2015). "Ageing impact on the antioxidant and antiproliferative properties of Port wines." *Food Research International* 67: 199-205.
- Pham, T. N., D. C. Nguyen, T. D. Lam, P. Van Thinh, X. T. Le, H. V. Quang, T. D. Nguyen and L. G. Bach (2019). Extraction of anthocyanins from Butterfly pea (*Clitoria ternatea* L. Flowers) in Southern Vietnam: Response surface modeling for optimization of the operation conditions. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, IOP Publishing.
- Saito, N., K. Abe, T. Honda, C. Timberlake and P. Bridle (1985). "Acylated delphinidin glucosides and flavonols from *Clitoria ternatea*."
- Tang, P. and M. M. Giusti (2020). "Metal chelates of petunidin derivatives exhibit enhanced color and stability." *Foods* 9(10): 1426.
- Terahara, N., N. Saito, T. Honda, K. Toki and Y. Osajima (1990). "Acylated anthocyanins of *Clitoria ternatea* flowers and their acyl moieties." *Phytochemistry* 29(3): 949-953.
- Tilbrook, J. and S. D. Tyerman (2008). "Cell death in grape berries: varietal differences linked to xylem pressure and berry weight loss." *Functional Plant Biology* 35(3): 173-184.
- Vidana Gamage, G. C., Y. Y. Lim and W. S. Choo (2021). "Anthocyanins from *Clitoria ternatea* flower: Biosynthesis, extraction, stability, antioxidant activity, and applications." *Frontiers in Plant Science* 12: 792303.
- Vidana Gamage, G. C., Y. Y. Lim and W. S. Choo (2022). "Sources and relative stabilities of acylated and nonacylated anthocyanins in beverage systems." *Journal of Food Science and Technology* 59(3): 831-845.

- Yoshida, K., M. Mori and T. Kondo (2009). "Blue flower color development by anthocyanins: from chemical structure to cell physiology." *Natural product reports* 26(7): 884-915.
- Zhu, H., T.-J. Zhang, J. Zheng, X.-D. Huang, Z.-C. Yu, C.-L. Peng and W. S. Chow (2018). "Anthocyanins function as a light attenuator to compensate for insufficient photoprotection mediated by nonphotochemical quenching in young leaves of *Acmena acuminatissima* in winter." *Photosynthetica* 56(1): 445-454.